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Preliminary investigations on natural fibre egg-box sandwich structures

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Abstract. This research describes the shear properties of coir-fibre, egg-box-core sandwich panels made of low-cost aluminium skins subjected to three-point bending (ASTM C393). This work is divided into two steps: (i) the manufacture of the egg-box composite structure and (ii) the sandwich panel. Unfilled and filled cores are investigated using castor-oil-based foam to fill the core voids. The shear properties determined by flexural tests and the bulk density are used to assess the mechanical performance of the sandwich structures. The biobased polymer provides adequate core-skin adhesion. Despite a slight increase in bulk density (4%), the castor-oil foam filling enhances the shear properties of the sandwich panels, with an increase of approximately 213% in shear strength and facing stress compared to unfilled panels. The increased contact area between the coir egg-box core and aluminium skins leads to higher shear load transfer along the skins, with a consequent increase in bending load.

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1. Introduction

Sandwich composite structures with low-density core materials have recently gained attention due to their attractive properties as superior energy absorption and out-of-plane loading levels upon flexural loads [1]. In sandwich panels, faces are the load-bearing structures, while the core should resist compressive and shear loads. The core should also support the face sheets to reduce crack propagation [2]. Various geometric configurations for the core have been investigated as more effective lightweight energy absorbing structures. Particular attention is

given to sandwich panels with the lightweight egg-box core design owing to their potential applications, such as in the aerospace and automotive industries [3].

Sandwich cores based on composite materials may provide outstanding mechanical properties under dynamic conditions [2]. Polymeric composites, in particular, broaden the possibilities of core manufacturing, owing to their easy conformation to different shapes and geometries [1]. Polymeric foams have been widely applied in combination with the core in sandwich structures to produce lightweight panels that can resist high loads under large strains before collapse [3]. Such association also makes promising energy-absorbing structures. Synthetic fibres are commonly used to fabricate these cores. Synthetic fibre-reinforced, epoxy egg-box cores have already been proposed (e.g., carbon and glass) [1-4].

In consonance with the increasing environmental concerns, this study proposes a novel sustainable sandwich structure made with a coir-fibre epoxy composite, egg-box core, bonded to aluminium facings (ISO 1200) using a contact adhesive. Unfilled and filled cores are investigated using a bio-based castor-oil foam to fill the core voids. To the best of these authors' knowledge, this is a pioneer investigation on sandwich panels with this aluminium alloy and egg-box core composed of natural fibre composites.

2. Methodology

Fig. 1. (a) Nylon matching mould in egg-box format; (b) corrugated coir egg-box composite; (c) sandwich structure with castor oil foam filled core.

A coir-fibre mat supplied by Deflor Bioengenharia (Brazil) is used as reinforcement. The mean length of the fibre filament is 160 ± 50 mm [5]. The epoxy adhesive (RenLam M and Aradur HY 956 hardener), provided by Huntsman (São Paulo, Brazil), is used as a matrix phase. The castor-oil foam Mamonex RD 70 supplied by Imperveg (São Paulo, Brazil) is used as a core filler agent. Coir-fibre-reinforced epoxy composites are modelled in an egg-box shape using a nylon mould, as described in Figure 1a, consisting of two complementary (positive and negative) parts. The egg-box corrugated core (Figure 1b) is manufactured through cold pressing at a uniaxial pressure of 645 kPa. The size of the egg-box mould is 150 (length) x 90 (width) x 10 (height) mm³. The fibre-matrix volume fraction used for coir egg-box core composites is 30%/70%, calculated based on the coir fibre density of 0.86 g/cm³ and

fibre weight of 12 g [6]. Facings and core are bonded using a simple contact adhesive (3M) with subsequent uniaxial compaction for 24 hours. Corrugated fillers are also used, manufactured using Mamonex RD 70. The responses evaluated in this work are bulk density, core shear and facing stress under three-point bending. Samples were weighed before tests to determine the bulk density. Flexural tests follow sample dimensions and recommendations preconised by ASTM C393 [7]. Rectangular samples of dimensions 150 x 90 mm are tested using a span length of 100 mm at a cross-head speed of 6 mm/min. Student's t-test is used for the statistical analysis using the Minitab 18 software.

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1 presents the mean values of the physical and mechanical properties of the investigated sandwich structures. The student's t-test reveals that the foam filler significantly increases the bulk density, shear strength and facing stress of the sandwich panels (p -value is zero). However, even though a slight increase in bulk density is observed (4.08%), the dramatic increase (213%) in shear strength and facing stress provided by the castor-oil foam is worth noting. Due to its porous structure, this rigid, low-density filler agent presents a high surface-volume ratio, reducing internal voids in the corrugated core and increasing the face-core contact area.

The defects in the corrugated core composite (Figure 1b) can be attributed to the manufacturing process. Superficial voids are present due to the viscosity of the resin at room temperature and friction during uniaxial cold pressing. The friction on the surface of the mould and coir fibres may hinder the resin flow and result in superficial defects. This problem has been solved by applying a thin resin layer (discounted from the 70% stipulated for the manufacturing process) over the nylon mould before pressing.

In bending, the top side of the beam, subjected to compressive stress, achieves higher strength with a filled core, attributed to the shear strengthening of the core [1–3]. The foam tends to increase the density due to the closed pores, enhancing the compressive strength of the top facing. In addition, foam-filled egg-box panels can experience higher transverse loads than unfilled panels [3].

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of coir egg-box sandwich panels.

	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Shear Strength (MPa)	Facing Stress (MPa)
Without foam-filling	0.494 (0.002)	0.19 (0.02)	18.6 (1.9)
With foam-filling	0.507 (0.002)	0.58 (0.02)	58.3 (2.5)
T-Student analysis (p -value)	0.000	0.000	0.000

4. Conclusions

This study investigates sustainable egg-box-core sandwich panels with and without castor oil biobased foam filler. Physical and mechanical tests are performed. The following conclusions are drawn:

- The facing stress of the panels is significantly increased (213%) due to the foam densification. In bending, when the core suffers a local flattening, the foam tends to increase the density due to the closed pores and consequently enhance the compressive strength of the top facing.

- Castor oil foam increases the contact area between the aluminium facings and the core providing high shear properties.
- The castor foam filler slightly increases the density of the studied sandwich panels (4.08%).

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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